

1 **Transformation in humans is associated with induction of photoreceptors and retinal genes of the**
2 **visual system.**

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7 Light is detected by the use of cones and rods that transmit visual spectrum energy to a chemical signal in
8 the retina. Rods function in scotopic vision (sight in low-light conditions), while cones function in color
9 vision and photo topic vision (high acuity sight). Rods utilize rhodopsin, encoded by RH1, for light
10 detection while cones detect light or electromagnetic waves in the visible spectrum using genes known as
11 opsins that encoded cones that detect long, medium and short waves.

12 We used primary tissues from humans with germline mutation of mismatch repair pathway machinery
13 isolated at different stages of neoplastic progression (pre-cancer or advanced pre-cancer) prior to the
14 onset of neoplasia as an in vivo model to study transformation as it proceeds in humans at the whole
15 transcriptome level. We observed unusually high induction of opsin.

Results

I. The genes most abundantly activated during transformation in vivo that functioned in the human visual system were opsin genes that encoded for medium and long wave cones. Rhodopsin (RH1) was produced in relatively small quantity and its induction was not significant.

Opsins

Opsins that detect medium waves

OPN1MW
OPN1MW2
OPN1MW3

Opsins that detect long waves

OPN1LW

II. Other genes that functioned in perception of light that were activated early in transformation in vivo were genes with expression in humans restricted to the retina.

Genes important for function of the retina

Retinal G protein RGR
Retinoid isomerohydrolase RPE65.
Retinal outer segment membrane protein ROM1.

III. Light detection by the visual system is characterized by expression of genes outside of the opsin family or retinal genes which were also targets of early activation during transformation in vivo, including genes that function in retinal ganglion cells in detection of short wavelength ("blue") light.

IV. A major photopigment, melanopsin (OPN4), encoded by OPN4 was not activated in vivo during transformation, but other molecules important for photodetection in retinal ganglion cells or otherwise were highly activated, including CNGA3. CNGA3 functions in a conserved light detection system in retinal ganglion cells with a second molecule, GNAT2. GNAT2 was not induced but a second GNAT family gene, GNAT3, was highly transcriptionally activated during early transformation in humans in vivo.

ABCA4, GUCY2D, CNGB3, and CACNA1F were also targets of modulation.

V. Photoreceptor gene activation during transformation in vivo included induction of PCARE, photoreceptor disc component PRCD and interphotoreceptor matrix proteoglycan IMPG2.

VI. Other visual system genes found to be activated early in the course of transformation in a human with pre-cancer was a homeobox transcription factor that supports differentiation to visual system during development in humans, VSX1, and a molecule that functions in the vitreous humor, opticin.

Discussion

We did not assay for any visual system capability by tumors, nor study whether the components expressed assembled into any functional photodetection system. The relative enrichment of opsin, retinal and photoreceptor genes at the transcriptome level and the abundant nature of their expression still prompted characterization of visual system gene activation in humans in vivo, early in transformation.

Binary determinations of the presence and absence of light in humans through the visual system independent of image formation have known physiologic functions that permit regulation of biologic activity based on light perception.